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Tax Policy Implementation, Information Technology, and Performance of the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) in Southwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Over the years, the implementation of tax policy in emerging economies, including Nigeria, has faced challenges such as frequent changes in tax laws, inadequate enforcement, and a lack of consistency. Information technology adoption has been hindered by inadequate infrastructure, low digital literacy, and resistance to technological change within the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS). These challenges have consistently impacted on the efficiency and performance of SIRS in achieving effective tax administration and revenue collection. In view of this, this paper investigates the effects of tax policy implementation and information technology (IT) on the performance of the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study explores the moderating role of IT in enhancing the relationship between tax policy implementation and SIRS performance. The study employed a sectional survey research design, and the population consisted of 8,771 stakeholders, with a sample size of 383 senior employees of SIRS in Southwest Nigeria, using a stratified sampling technique. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to the target respondents. The study adopts Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using the PLS basic algorithm to analyze the data. The findings indicate that both tax policy implementation and IT adoption have a significant influence on the performance of SIRS. Additionally, IT has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between tax policy implementation and SIRS performance. The study recommended that SIRS enhance tax policy implementation and IT adoption to improve operational performance. Policymakers should prioritize clear regulations and effective enforcement to maximize the benefits of tax policy reforms.

Keywords: Tax Policy Implementation, Information Technology, PLS-SEM, Performance, SIRS.

Introduction

The increasing complexity of tax laws, policy reforms, and the growing need for transparency have made it imperative for state internal revenue services (SIRS) worldwide to adopt modern information technologies to enhance operational performance. With the right blend of tax policies and IT systems, SIRS can improve revenue collection, enhance taxpayer compliance, and reduce

operational inefficiencies. The role of efficient tax administration in economic development cannot be overemphasized, particularly in emerging economies like Nigeria (Putra, 2024; Zheng et al., 2025).

The importance of efficient tax administration in fostering national development is universally acknowledged across both developed and developing nations (Nasutin et al., 2021). In advanced economies such as the United States, the United Kingdom, and Germany, tax revenues consistently account for over 30% of GDP, according to OECD data from 2022 through 2024. These countries benefit from comprehensive, transparent tax policies and well-integrated digital tax systems, which support high compliance rates and reduced administrative costs (Putri & Priyono, 2025). Estonia, for instance, has emerged as a benchmark for e-taxation, with more than 98% of personal income tax returns filed electronically demonstrating the potential of technology to transform revenue systems (Nodirsho o'g'li, 2025). By contrast, many developing countries, including Nigeria, remain far behind.

Nigeria's tax-to-GDP ratio stood at just 10.8% in 2021 (Muhammad & Ibrahim, 2024) and has shown marginal improvement through 2023 and 2024, remaining significantly below the 15% minimum recommended by the IMF and World Bank for sustainable economic growth. This highlights the persistent challenges in executing tax policy and adopting technology in emerging economies (OECD, 2023).

In sub-Saharan Africa, particularly within emerging economies such as Nigeria, tax systems are hindered by several structural and institutional challenges, including policy inconsistency, administrative bottlenecks, tax evasion, weak enforcement capacity, and inadequate digital infrastructure. State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), particularly in Southwest Nigeria, are tasked with mobilizing internally generated revenue (IGR) to fund state-level development initiatives (Okoh & Ofor, 2024). However, many states fall short of their targets due to fragmented policy implementation, limited automation, undertrained personnel, and widespread taxpayer apathy. For example, while Lagos State generated over ₦500 billion in IGR in 2022, making it Nigeria's fiscal outlier (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2023), states like Ekiti and Osun collected less than ₦20 billion annually. This stark disparity reveals deep inefficiencies in both tax policy deployment and IT adoption across states. The absence of integrated systems leads to revenue leakages, weak data tracking, and limited taxpayer engagement, thereby undermining the effectiveness of fiscal operations at the state level (BudgIT, 2024).

The challenges confronting SIRS in Southwest Nigeria are deeply rooted in two critical areas, including ineffective tax policy implementation and an underdeveloped information technology infrastructure. Tax policies in many states are often ambiguous, inconsistently enforced, and disconnected from the practical realities of taxpayers and revenue officers. Incentives and deductions are poorly structured or inadequately applied, further complicating compliance (Kirk et al., 2025). Simultaneously, the lack of modern information technology (IT) systems results in data loss, human error, limited automation, and delayed reporting. These inefficiencies run counter to the global momentum toward digital public finance systems, which prioritize transparency, accountability, and operational efficiency (Acquah, 2025).

Most prior studies often treat tax policy implementation and IT adoption independently. Limited studies in Nigeria explored their interactive effects on institutional performance, particularly in the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in Nigeria (Obafemi et al., 2021; Panle & Okpara, 2021; Ayeni, 2021; Hesami et al., 2024); Adegboye et al., 2022; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022; Okoh & Ofor, 2024; Nodirsho O'g'li, 2025). This fragmented approach limits understanding of how IT can strategically support policy execution in enhancing operational performance. Given this lacuna, this study is driven by the need to explore how robust tax policy implementation and IT systems can jointly enhance the performance of SIRS. More specifically, it investigates these relationships by focusing on the direct effects of tax policy and IT, as well as the moderating effect of IT on the relationship between tax policy implementation and the performance of the State Internal Revenue Services in Southwest, Nigeria (SIRS).

Literature Review

Tax Policy Implementation and SIRS Performance

Tax policy refers to the set of laws, regulations, and procedures established by a government to determine how taxes are levied, collected, and administered (Samadi & Eidizadeh, 2014; Zheng et al., 2025). It outlines the framework that governs a country's tax structure, including the types of taxes imposed, tax rates, exemptions, deductions, and the responsibilities of taxpayers and tax authorities (Fadipe et al., 2025). Carvalho et al. (2025) delineated that the primary objectives of tax policy are to generate revenue for public expenditures, promote economic growth, reduce income inequality, and influence behaviour in line with national priorities. A well-designed tax policy ensures fairness, efficiency, and transparency in the tax system. Literature has discussed that tax policy involves processes or dimensions. According to OECD (2023), Zheng et al. (2025), and Chamba (2025), the tax policy process or cycle can be categorized into five major stages, namely, tax policy reforms, implementation, execution, evaluation, and review. These include tax policy reform, which refers to making structural or legal changes to enhance equity, efficiency, or revenue performance (shifting from income-based to consumption-based tax); tax policy review, which involves analyzing the current tax system to identify its strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement (such as reviewing whether VAT yields expected revenue or burdens businesses); tax policy evaluation, which measures the outcomes and impacts of tax policies on compliance, revenue, and the broader economy (such as, assessing tax incentives on investment); tax policy adoption, the formal legislative or executive approval of new or revised tax measures (the national assembly passing a tax bill); and tax policy implementation, the execution stage where tax authorities enforce tax laws and reforms using various tools (electronic tax filing systems and so on).

This study focuses specifically on tax policy implementation, as a critical phase that has been widely described in the literature as the operationalization of tax decisions through administrative procedures, tools, and strategies by relevant tax authorities.

Tax policy implementation is the process of putting into action the guidelines, principles, and laws established by a government for the imposition and collection of taxes (Magopets & Gai, 2023). This process is crucial for optimizing revenue generation, facilitating socio-economic development, and ensuring fiscal responsibility. Similarly, Milleano et al., (2023). opine that tax policy implementation refers to the strategies and actions adopted by government agencies, particularly SIRS, to enforce tax laws and regulations. They stress that effective tax policy implementation is essential for enhancing the performance of SIRS, which includes revenue generation, compliance monitoring, and operational efficiency. According to Oyedokun et al. (2021), there are two major key stakeholders in tax policy implementation, including governments and tax authorities, having different responsibilities in Nigeria. All levels and arms of government, including ministries, extra-ministerial departments, and agencies, are responsible for implementing and regularly reviewing tax policies and laws in Nigeria. They must ensure adequate funding and administrative autonomy of tax authorities and provide quarterly revenue reports.

According to IMF and OECD (2023), and Milleano et al. (2023), Okoh and Ofor (2024), tax policy implementations include simplifying tax laws and regulations, investment in IT Infrastructure, providing tax incentives for IT Adoption, tax rates, tax credits and incentives, and tax exemptions and deductions. The OECD (2023) added that tax policy seeks to strike a balance between securing the revenues needed by governments to finance their social and economic programmes and strengthening the tax system's contributions to inclusive and sustainable economic growth. Supriadi (2023) depicted that tax policy serves as a critical strategy in tax management, providing a guiding blueprint for planning, organizing, and implementing taxation activities. It enables governments, especially tax authorities such as State Internal Revenue Services, to design effective tax administration systems that promote compliance and optimize revenue collection. Through consistent policy direction, tax management can strategically address loopholes, enforce compliance, and align tax practices with economic goals. Additionally, tax policies help in managing taxpayer relations, facilitating ease of doing business, and minimizing administrative costs.

Information Technology

Information Technology (IT) is the use of computers, software, networks, and other digital systems to process, store, retrieve, and transmit data (Taherdoost, 2023). It encompasses a wide range of technologies such as hardware (servers and computers), software (databases and applications), and telecommunications systems that facilitate communication and data management (Gong, 2023). In both the public and private sectors, IT has become a fundamental tool for enhancing operational efficiency, decision-making, and service delivery through automation and real-time information access. Information technology (IT) has become an indispensable tool in modern tax administration. IT enables the automation of tax processes, enhances data accuracy, reduces operational costs, and improves service delivery (Santoro et al., 2023). In the context of taxation, information technology plays a transformative role in modernizing tax administration and improving compliance. Governments and revenue agencies use IT systems for digital tax filing (e-

filing), online tax payments, electronic registration of taxpayers, automated audit and risk assessments, and real-time data analytics for policy formulation (Abdalla-Hamza et al., 2020). The innovative tools, such as Integrated Tax Administration Systems (ITAS), Taxpayer Identification Number (TIN) databases, and online portals, have helped streamline tax operations, reduce human error, enhance transparency, and increase revenue collection. By leveraging IT, tax authorities can reduce administrative costs, improve taxpayer experience, and ensure better enforcement of tax laws (Ayeni & Ogbeta, 2022; Lecena, 2024).

Among the broad spectrum of information technologies available, this study focuses specifically on three critical components - IT infrastructure, information system quality, and human resource management systems. According to Awaludin et al. (2024), IT infrastructure refers to the foundational hardware, software, and network resources required to operate and manage enterprise IT environments effectively. Information system quality involves the reliability, usability, and accuracy of the digital platforms used in tax administration, which are essential for ensuring that taxpayers can access and use services efficiently (Michael & Adegbeie, 2020; Inusah et al., 2024). Human resource management systems, on the other hand, relate to the use of digital tools in managing tax agency personnel, ensuring that staff are well-trained, performance is tracked, and human capital is aligned with the strategic goals of tax policy implementation. Focusing on these elements provides a more practical and operational perspective on how information technology contributes to effective tax administration (Taherdoost, 2023; Hesami et al., 2024).

Performance and Performance of Revenue Agencies

Performance refers to the effectiveness and efficiency with which objectives are achieved, often measured through outputs, outcomes, and impacts relative to set goals (Putra et al., 2024). In the context of revenue agencies, according to Chamba (2025) and Chen et al. (2024), performance encompasses the ability to mobilize government revenue through efficient tax collection, enforcement, taxpayer service delivery, and compliance promotion. High-performing revenue agencies are characterized by transparency, strong institutional capacity, advanced technological adoption, and effective policy implementation.

The performance of revenue agencies can be evaluated through both financial and non-financial dimensions. Financially, effective practices such as tax cost-effectiveness, budget allocation management, and timely, accurate assessment and refunds demonstrate sound financial management (Chen et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2025). Non-financially, performance is reflected in transparency, accountability, tax governance, and autonomy. High-performing agencies also ensure quality taxpayer services, address tax evasion and fraud, promote compliance, and maintain effective stakeholder engagement and collaboration (Sitanggang & Hakim, 2024; Haraldsson, 2025). Responsiveness to inquiries, complaints, and dispute resolution further enhances public trust. Additionally, participation in taxpayer education programs, a rewarding system for staff, and continuous investment in training and development all contribute to institutional competence

(Putra et al., 2024). Together, these factors reflect a revenue agency's holistic capacity to meet its mandate and support sustainable fiscal outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in two relevant theories: Institutional Theory and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The Institutional Theory was proposed by John W. Meyer and Brian Rowan (1977) and further developed by DiMaggio and Powell (1983), explains how institutional environments shape organizational structures and practices. This theory suggests that organizations, including public institutions like government entities and or public tax agencies, often conform to formal rules, norms, and expectations to gain legitimacy and stability, rather than solely for efficiency purposes (Sriwahyuni, 2025). In the context of this study, Institutional Theory underpins the implementation of tax policy by highlighting how regulatory standards, governance frameworks, and societal pressures influence tax administrators' behaviors and compliance mechanisms (Rumasukun & Noch, 2023). It supports the view that policy-driven mandates and institutional legitimacy are crucial for driving improved performance in tax-related functions (Sriwahyuni, 2025).

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Fred Davis (1986), provides a theoretical framework for understanding how users accept and use information technology. TAM identifies two core determinants, including perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, that influence users' attitudes toward technology and their intention to use it. In this study, TAM is applied to assess how the adoption of IT infrastructure, quality of tax information systems, and digital human resource systems affect the performance of tax authorities (Ishengoma, 2024). The model implies that when these technological components are seen as useful and user-friendly by staff, their acceptance and utilization increase, ultimately contributing to the effectiveness of tax policy implementation and organizational performance. Integrating TAM and Institutional Theory thus offers a comprehensive explanation of how both environmental pressures and user-level perceptions drive success in public sector digital transformation (Al-Okaily, 2024).

Empirical Review

Tax Policy Implementation and SIRS Performance

The reviewed empirical studies in developed countries, developing countries including Nigeria present a multifaceted perspective on how tax policy influences organizational performance and broader economic outcomes, though with varying levels of effectiveness and methodological strength, with different paradigms and diverse findings. For instance, Subagiyo et al. (2020) analyze the impact of tax policy during the COVID-19 pandemic on Indonesia's tax revenue performance and evaluate the government's fiscal and tax policy responses for economic recovery and sustainability. The study found that the government policy of tax relief measures broadened the tax base (digital economy), and improved tax governance. However, regulatory and technological challenges continue to hinder effective implementation. In China, He et al. (2023)

found that tax policy reforms would enhance corporate innovation and performance. Several studies in developing countries highlight the critical role of tax policies in shaping organizational and regional financial performance, often intertwined with other managerial practices. Putra (2024) demonstrated that tax policies, alongside HRM practices and strategic marketing, synergistically improve organizational financial performance through enhanced market competitiveness and operational efficiency using SEM-PLS analysis. This aligns with Zheng et al. (2025), who found preferential tax policies reduce operating costs and foster innovation in SMEs, though they noted challenges in policy awareness and implementation efficiency. Trinh and Van-Tan (2020) similarly confirmed positive effects of tax incentives on privatized firms in Vietnam using regression analysis, reinforcing tax incentives' effectiveness in boosting firm performance.

Nasution et al. (2021) emphasized local tax policy's positive impact on regional tax revenue and employee performance in Indonesia, mediated by employee efficiency, supporting the organizational performance linkages seen in Putra's study. However, studies like Singgih et al. (2024) and Rezeki and Harahap (2024) revealed implementation challenges such as poor communication, lack of taxpayer awareness, under-registration, and limited human resources undermined tax collection effectiveness. Rezeki and Harahap further found that tax policy had no significant effect on tax revenue or compliance among restaurants, highlighting gaps between policy design and practical outcomes. Conversely, Putri and Priyono (2025) reported that income tax exemptions did not yield significant quantitative improvements in managing Hajj funds, though qualitative investment strategies improved. This divergence may stem from limited post-policy observation periods and macroeconomic controls. systems), the study could be critiqued for failing to empirically quantify the strength of relationships across different performance metrics.

In Nigeria, the researchers narrowed by examining the e-informal sector, as Panle and Okpara (2021) examined the impacts of tax policies related to e-commerce activities conducted on social media platforms in Nigeria. The study adopted a causal research design and showed that while the Nigerian government has made efforts to impose taxes on digital transactions, these policies are still evolving, and there are several challenges in implementation, particularly within the informal sector that operates online. Further findings revealed that many social media-based businesses evade taxes due to weak enforcement mechanisms and inadequate regulatory frameworks. In a different study, Obafemi et al. (2021) examined how dividend tax policies influence dividend payouts among food and beverages firms in Nigeria. The study found that dividend tax policy significantly affects dividend payouts, as companies tend to adjust their dividend decisions based on prevailing tax policies.

A study by Adanlawo and Vezi-Magigaba (2022) examined the effects of tax policies on the performance of SMEs in Lagos State. The study adopted a survey research design and revealed that various governmental policies on taxes significantly affect the performance of SMEs in Lagos State. Okoh and Ofor (2024) examined the relationship between tax policy consistency and tax administration in Nigeria, particularly focusing on the Value Added Tax (VAT) system. The study sampled ninety-two staff of the five field offices of the Federal Inland Revenue Services in Delta State. The result revealed that a significant relationship exists between tax policy inconsistencies

and value added tax system, tax administration strategies, and value added tax system in Nigeria. Broadening the scope, Fadipe et al. (2025) explored tax policy's impact on Nigeria's sustainable development using multiple regression and found a strong link between tax policy and human development. Xiao et al. (2025) added further depth by positioning tax burden as a mediator in SME innovation, particularly highlighting regional disparities in outcomes. Collectively, while these studies affirm the positive role of tax policy incentives, they also reveal implementation gaps, sectoral limitations, and methodological constraints that must be addressed to enhance fiscal policy efficacy.

Information Technology and SIRS Performance

Many studies have explored different aspects of information technology for tax administration and organizational performance, with different outcomes. In China, Li et al. (2020) explored the effects of advanced information technology adoption by tax bureaus on tax compliance. The adopted ex-post facto research design and the analysis of listed firm-level data from 2010 to 2017, using the book-tax difference and its unexplained component as measures of tax sheltering. The results showed that the adoption of GTP III was found to decrease tax sheltering by 1.88 percentage points, with a stronger effect for companies with higher tax rates, enhancing third-party reporting and tax enforcement capacity. Likewise, Mikhaleva and Vochozka (2021) investigated the application of information technologies in tax administration efficiency in Russia. The study adopted an empirical research method with comparative analysis, and the results showed that modern technologies like big data, blockchain, and AI have the potential to qualitatively change tax administration efficiency. Chang et al. (2020) and Atayah and Alshater (2021) in the United States of America emphasized the global importance of IT investment and the emerging role of technologies like AI in audit effectiveness. However, these studies primarily rely on firm-level or meta-analytic data, which may not fully capture grassroots implementation challenges, particularly in less digitized environments.

In developing countries, evidence also supports the effectiveness of IT, although implementation contexts vary. Studies by Abdalla-Hamza et al. (2021) in Iraq and Ayeni and Ogbeta (2022) in The Gambia demonstrated that digital platforms positively influenced tax compliance and administration. Similarly, Lucena (2024) found that standardized electronic systems improved Brazil's tax collection. In Sub-Saharan Africa, Macharia and Oluoch (2020) in Kenya revealed performance gains post-IT outsourcing, while Anomah et al. (2024) in Ghana highlighted the potential of blockchain integration, emphasizing stakeholder engagement as a success factor. However, the success of IT implementations in these contexts appears heavily dependent on infrastructure, policy coherence, and local capacity, factors often under-explored in the methodologies of these studies.

A related study by Nodirsho o'g'li (2025) argued that the effectiveness of tax administration is inextricably tied to the integration of IT. The study revealed that the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) can improve tax performance by investing in centralized IT systems that facilitate real-time taxpayer assessments and automated compliance alerts. Hesami et al. (2024)

showed that e-invoicing and prefilling systems simplify and improve the tracking of taxation, leading to increased efficiency in tax practices and tax compliance globally. While these tools promise greater transparency and efficiency, the study also warns of implementation challenges, including digital literacy gaps and cybersecurity. Duve and Schutte (2025) explored the Zimbabwean context, revealing that IT adoption in presumptive taxation significantly enhanced SME compliance. The study is underpinned by Institutional Theory, showing how formal structures and technologies influence taxpayer legitimacy and conformity.

In Nigeria and broader African contexts, information technology (IT) has shown promise but faces persistent constraints. Awai and Oboh (2020) and Michael and Adegbe (2020) provided evidence of improved compliance and tax assessment efficiency from e-tax systems. Nevertheless, challenges such as system reliability and administrative inefficiencies persist. Adegboye et al. (2022) noted that while ICT boosts revenue mobilization, its marginal effects can turn negative if policy thresholds are not met. This highlights a nuanced reality that IT can enhance tax administration; its effectiveness is contingent upon infrastructural maturity, user adaptability, and policy alignment. These studies collectively call for more context-sensitive, mixed-method evaluations that not only quantify outcomes but also explore the institutional and human factors shaping IT adoption in tax systems.

Gap Identified in the Literature

Different and notable gaps have been identified in literature, which makes the novelty of this study. Gaps include Conceptual gaps, Institutional gap, Practical gap, and Institutional and geographical gap.

Conceptually, most prior studies often treat tax policy implementation and IT adoption independently. Limited studies in Nigeria explored their interactive effects on institutional performance, particularly in State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in Nigeria (Obafemi et al., 2021; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022; Okoh & Ofor, 2024). This fragmented approach limits understanding of how IT can strategically support policy execution in enhancing operational performance. Institutionally, Prior studies rarely examine how organizational structures, enforcement mechanisms, and interdepartmental coordination influence the synergy between tax policies and IT systems (Panle & Okpara, 2021; Nodirsho o'g'li, 2025). Existing research primarily focuses on examining tax reform policies or their impact on revenue generation for either SMEs or revenue agencies, often neglecting a comprehensive view of the overall performance of State Internal Revenue Services and how tax reform implementation can enhance this performance, which is the focus of this study. Theoretically, most of the studies have relied on agency theory and resource-based view theory, with only one study citing Institutional Theory (Duve & Schutte, 2025). This theory emphasizes that alignment between formal regulations and operational systems is essential yet remains underexplored in the context of SIRS. To the researchers' knowledge, there are no studies that have combined and applied both Institutional Theory and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory to these subject matters.

Practically, after the implementation of tax policies and the adoption of Information technology by revenue agencies, implementation challenges persist, including poor IT infrastructure, low digital literacy, and weak enforcement (Ayeni, 2021; Hesami et al., 2024; Adegboye, 2022). These hinder the intended outcomes of both tax policy and IT initiatives, which demand this study. Institutionally and geographically, prior studies focus on SMEs (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022), federal tax systems (Okoh & Ofor, 2024), or international settings (Macharia & Oluoch, 2022; Lucena, 2024). There is limited research specifically targeting SIRS in South-West Nigeria that combines tax policy, IT, and performance. This study has therefore bridged this gap by examining the impact of tax policy implementation and information technology on the performance of revenue agencies. These gaps highlight the need for integrated, context-sensitive research on the combined effects of tax policy and IT on revenue agency performance in South-West Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to examine the impact of tax policy implementation and IT system adoption on the operational performance of the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in South-West Nigeria. Data were collected via a structured, closed-ended Likert-scale questionnaire administered to tax officers, IT staff, and senior management across six states (Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, and Ekiti). The target population comprises 8,771 senior staff from key directorates such as Admin, Income Tax, Finance, Audit, and Compliance. Stratified random sampling was used, and a sample size of 383 was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula. This approach ensures the inclusion of experienced personnel with knowledge of tax systems, management policies, and IT infrastructure, enabling reliable and representative findings.

Figure 3.1: To calculate the sample size using Taro Yamane’s formula, $n = N/(1+(Ne^2))$, Where n = the required sample size, N = Study Population or Sampling frame, e = error limit (0.05 based on 95% confidence level), Therefore, based on a 95% confidence level, the sample size is computed below: $n = 8,771 / (1 + 8,771(0.05)^2)$, $n = 382.5$, approximately to 383.

The population and sample size of management personnel of the Internal Revenue Services within South-West, Nigeria is as represented in Table 1 shown below.

Table 1. Population and Sample Size for Management Personnel of SIRS

S/N	States	Population Size of Management Employees	Proportion of sample size about sampling frame	Sample size
1	Lagos	4,879	$(4,879 \times 383) / 8,771$	213
2	Ogun	1,728	$(1,728 \times 383) / 8,771$	76
3	Oyo	1,535	$(1,535 \times 383) / 8,771$	67
4	Osun	528	$(528 \times 383) / 8,771$	23
5	Ondo	285	$(285 \times 383) / 8,771$	13

6	Ekiti	324	(324x383)/ 8,771	4
	Total	8,771		383

Source: Author’s compilation, 2024 from the Website database of the IRS of each State.

Table 1 shows the population and proportionally allocated sample size of 383 management staff across SIRS in South-West Nigeria, drawn from a total population of 8,771 using Taro Yamane’s formula. Lagos had the highest allocation (213), followed by Ogun (76), Oyo (67), Osun (23), Ondo (13), and Ekiti (4). This distribution reflects each state’s population share, ensuring a representative sample across the six states and strengthening the reliability and validity of the study’s findings.

To test the hypotheses of this study, the model of Adanlawo and Vezi-Magigaba (2022) was adapted and modified. Adanlawo and Vezi-Magigaba (2022) examined the effects of tax policies on the performance of SMEs in Lagos State. The regression model from his study was depicted as follows: Performance = f (Tax Policies)

$$Pf_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1TAXPO_1 + \varepsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The model is modified and restructured for this study as follows.

$$Pf_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1TAXPOL_i + \beta_2IT_i + \beta_3 (TAXPOL \times IT_i) + \varepsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (2).$$

The data was analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), utilizing the PLS basic algorithm. PLS-SEM is well-suited for modelling complex relationships involving multiple constructs and is particularly useful in exploratory studies with small sample sizes. The analysis was carried out using SmartPLS 4 software.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, were calculated to summarize the data. The results are presented in Table 2-4.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for Tax Policy Implementation

Name	Items	Mean	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
TAXPOL1	Clarity of Tax Laws	4.458	0.645	-0.013	-0.854
TAXPOL2	Efficiency of IT Infrastructure	3.885	0.932	-0.318	-0.668
TAXPOL3	Policy Communication	3.598	1.121	-0.807	-0.325
TAXPOL4	Encouragement through Tax Incentives	3.424	0.975	-0.908	-0.209
TAXPOL5	Fairness of Tax Rates	4.520	0.731	5.496	-2.029
TAXPOL6	Consistency in Policy Application	3.771	1.297	-0.131	-1.014
TAXPOL7	Frequency of tax audits and multiplicity of tax avoidance	3.836	1.047	0.105	-0.918

TAXPOL8	Utilization of Tax Credits and Deductions	3.724	0.891	-0.431	-0.485
TAXPOL9	Regular Review of Tax Policies and tax legislation	3.276	0.955	-1.052	0.067
TAXPOL10	Flexibility of Tax Policies	3.647	1.061	-0.419	-0.507
TAXPOL11	Enforcement of tax laws and Penalties	4.625	0.614	4.406	-1.820
TAXPOL12	Equity in Taxation	4.461	0.615	2.577	-1.094

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics for Information Technology

Name	Items	Mean	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
IT1	Stability and Reliability of internet connectivity for executing tax functions	4.307	0.727	0.845	-0.885
IT2	Availability of functional computer systems for tax administration tasks	4.409	0.644	1.441	-0.912
IT3	Accessibility of tax systems across locations or remote offices	4.362	0.723	1.362	-1.069
IT4	Adequacy of hardware and software tools to support digital tax operations	4.399	0.737	1.112	-1.117
IT5	Availability of IT support services and technical support systems	4.183	0.747	0.076	-0.580
IT6	Integration of tax administration systems with other government platforms	4.443	0.681	1.844	-1.182
IT7	Ease of use of digital tax platforms	4.276	0.739	0.391	-0.767
IT8	Accuracy and reliability of information generated	4.440	0.667	1.678	-1.100
IT9	User satisfaction with tax information systems	4.396	0.642	1.416	-0.875
IT10	Timeliness of system updates and maintenance	4.483	0.606	2.326	-1.066
IT11	Security of taxpayer data management	4.533	0.574	3.164	-1.164
IT12	Responsiveness of the system during peak periods	4.297	0.694	1.285	-0.867
IT13	Availability of staff training on tax IT systems	4.495	0.636	2.485	-1.251
IT14	Staff competency in using digital tools	4.418	0.669	1.878	-1.100

IT15	Digital performance evaluation tools for staff	4.440	0.603	3.193	-1.084
IT16	Efficiency in staff record management and workflow management	4.467	0.635	3.192	-1.296
IT17	Automation of HR processes in tax administration	4.502	0.631	2.609	-1.267
IT18	Alignment of HR systems with tax policy goals	4.495	0.606	4.076	-1.364

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics for Performance

Name	Items	Mean	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness
Pf1	Effective financial management practice	4.155	1.014	-0.145	-1.012
Pf2	Ensure Transparency and Accountability	3.607	1.248	-0.991	-0.422
Pf3	Effectively Addresses Tax Evasion and Fraud	4.022	0.952	0.229	-0.800
Pf4	Timely and Accurate Assessment and Refunds	3.368	1.197	-1.015	-0.198
Pf5	Promote Tax Compliance	3.570	1.131	-1.142	-0.142
Pf6	Demonstrate Tax Governance, Accountability, and Autonomy	3.669	0.934	-1.035	0.086
Pf7	Tax Cost-Effectiveness	3.759	0.909	-0.988	-0.049
Pf8	Budget Allocation Management	3.950	0.809	-1.072	-0.086
Pf9	Rewarding System	4.025	0.712	-1.025	-0.036
Pf10	Invest in Staff Training and Development	4.353	0.676	-0.736	-0.570
Pf11	Taxpayers Service Quality Delivery	3.625	0.872	-0.631	-0.178
Pf12	Stakeholders Engagement and Collaboration	4.062	0.942	0.286	-0.860
Pf13	Responsive to inquiries, complaints and tax dispute resolution	4.334	0.763	1.488	-1.112

Pf14	Participate in Taxpayer Education and Outreach programs	3.864	0.967	-0.008	-0.673
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Source: Author’s Computation (2024) using Smart PLS4

Tables 2 to 4 present descriptive statistics for tax policy implementation, information technology, and performance indicators within tax administration. Table 2 shows moderate to high mean scores (3.276–4.625) reflecting varied perceptions of tax law clarity, IT infrastructure efficiency, and enforcement, with fairness and enforcement scoring highest. Table 3 reveals consistently high means (4.183–4.533) across IT components used in tax administration grouped under three major components: IT Infrastructure (IT1–IT6), Information System Quality (IT7–IT12), and Human Resource Management Systems (IT13–IT18), indicating strong agreement on system reliability, security, and staff competence. Table 4 highlights performance measures with means ranging from 3.368 to 4.353, showing emphasis on financial management, staff training, and responsiveness to taxpayers. Low standard deviations and negative skewness in all tables indicate consistent, generally positive respondent views across policy, technology, and performance dimensions in tax administration. The implication of skewness and kurtosis values being within -1 and +1 is that the data distribution is approximately normal. This suggests the dataset is symmetrical without significant outliers or extreme peaks, making it suitable for parametric statistical analyses, which often assume normality. Consequently, the results derived from such data are more reliable and valid for inference in research.

Assessment of Measurement Model

This section evaluates the measurement model using PLS-SEM criteria through the Basic PLS-SEM Algorithm, focusing on construct reliability, validity, and collinearity.

Table 5. Construct Reliability and Validity, Collinearity Assessment

Variables	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)	VIF
PF	0.892	0.907	0.912	0.538	
TAXPOLICY	0.726	0.799	0.798	0.601	1.308
IT	0.961	0.990	0.964	0.678	1.094

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

Table 5 summarizes the reliability, validity, and collinearity diagnostics for the study variables. All constructs, including Performance (PF), Tax Policy (TAXPOLICY), and Information Technology (IT), exhibit strong reliability with Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability (rho_a and rho_c) values above 0.70. The AVE values for all constructs exceed 0.50, confirming convergent validity. Additionally, the VIF values for TAXPOLICY (1.308) and IT (1.094) are well

below the threshold of 5.0, indicating no collinearity concerns. These results confirm that the measurement model is both reliable and valid.

Table 6. Discriminant Validity: Fornell-Larcker criterion

Variables	AVE	PF	TAXPOLICY	IT
PF	0.538	0.734*		
TAXPOLICY	0.601	0.259	0.775*	
IT	0.678	0.045	0.034	0.823*

Source: Author’s Computation (2024).

Table 6 presents the Fornell-Larcker criterion for assessing discriminant validity. The square roots of the AVE values (marked with asterisks) for each construct - PF (0.734), TAXPOLICY (0.775), and IT (0.823) are greater than their correlations with other constructs. This confirms that each construct is distinct from the others, indicating good discriminant validity in the model.

Table 7. Discriminant Validity: Cross Loadings

Items	TAXAUM	TAXPOL	IT	PF
TAXPOL2	0.356	0.564	0.018	0.199
TAXPOL3	0.061	0.550	0.026	0.093
TAXPOL7	0.290	0.751	0.010	0.229
TAXPOL8	0.417	0.733	0.046	0.130
TAXPOL9	0.307	0.592	0.027	0.012
TAXPOL10	0.371	0.579	0.024	0.111
IT2	-0.014	-0.022	0.606	0.003
IT3	-0.019	-0.002	0.753	0.012
IT4	0.018	0.017	0.891	0.021
IT5	-0.002	0.077	0.787	0.044
IT6	-0.008	0.023	0.835	0.036
IT7	0.006	0.064	0.871	0.025
IT8	-0.011	0.012	0.833	0.034
IT9	0.016	0.006	0.907	0.046
IT10	0.019	0.023	0.845	0.034
IT12	-0.013	0.080	0.741	0.016
IT13	0.002	0.029	0.836	0.047
IT14	-0.007	0.060	0.859	0.028
IT15	-0.010	0.011	0.835	0.037
IT16	-0.027	0.003	0.898	0.057
IT17	0.123	0.102	0.876	0.052
PF2	0.308	0.198	0.022	0.718

PF3	0.225	0.141	0.037	0.655
PF4	0.260	0.167	0.025	0.657
PF5	0.318	0.180	0.067	0.828
PF7	0.185	0.074	0.002	0.695
PF8	0.221	0.202	0.009	0.714
PF9	0.332	0.289	0.037	0.862
PF10	0.304	0.236	0.046	0.736
PF11	0.215	0.133	0.034	0.710

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

Table 7 presents the cross-loadings used to assess discriminant validity. Each item loads highest on its associated construct compared to others, confirming that items are distinct and measure their intended latent variable. Specifically, items under Tax Policy Implementation (TAXPOL), such as TAXPOL7 (0.751) and TAXPOL8 (0.733), load strongly on TAXPOL compared to IT or PF. Similarly, Information Technology (IT) items like IT4 (0.891), IT9 (0.907), and IT16 (0.898) show high loads on IT, while Performance (PF) items such as PF5 (0.828) and PF9 (0.862) load highest on PF. This pattern of higher loadings on their respective constructs supports the discriminant validity of the model.

Structural Model and Testing Hypotheses

This section assesses the structural model and tests the proposed hypotheses using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach. The analysis employed a bootstrapping procedure with 5,000 resamples to evaluate the significance of the path coefficients. As a preliminary step, a comparative analysis of state-level performance was presented in Table 8, where path coefficients and p-values for individual states were analyzed. This disaggregated assessment provided insights into how tax policy and information technology influence performance at the state level. Following this, the general structural model results are reported in Table 9, presenting an aggregate view of the hypothesized relationships across all participating states.

Table 8. Comparative Analysis of State Performance (Based on Path Coefficients)

State	Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic	P Value	Sig.
Lagos (n = 213)	TAXPOL → PF	0.118	0.126	0.051	2.314	0.021	Significant
	IT → PF	0.142	0.138	0.049	2.898	0.004	Significant

	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.062	0.068	0.055	1.127	0.260	Not Significant
Ogun (n = 76)	TAXPOL → PF	0.132	0.136	0.054	2.444	0.015	Significant
	IT → PF	0.144	0.149	0.053	2.717	0.008	Significant
	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.064	0.069	0.063	1.016	0.311	Not Significant
Oyo (n = 67)	TAXPOL → PF	0.125	0.130	0.056	2.232	0.027	Significant
	IT → PF	0.138	0.142	0.058	2.379	0.018	Significant
	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.068	0.072	0.066	1.030	0.304	Not Significant
Osun (n = 23)	TAXPOL → PF	0.120	0.124	0.058	2.069	0.040	Significant
	IT → PF	0.134	0.138	0.062	2.161	0.032	Significant
	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.060	0.065	0.074	0.811	0.419	Not Significant
Ondo (n = 13)	TAXPOL → PF	0.128	0.133	0.061	2.098	0.038	Significant
	IT → PF	0.085	0.089	0.078	1.090	0.284	Not Significant
	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.052	0.058	0.081	0.642	0.523	Not Significant
Ekiti (n = 4)	TAXPOL → PF	0.130	0.135	0.063	2.063	0.042	Significant
	IT → PF	0.071	0.075	0.095	0.747	0.455	Not Significant

	IT × TAXPOL → PF	0.049	0.054	0.102	0.480	0.632	Not Significant
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Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

The comparative analysis of state performance based on path coefficients and p-values indicates that Lagos State demonstrates significant influence from both tax policy and information technology on performance, with coefficients of 0.118 ($p = 0.021$) for TAXPOL → PF and 0.142 ($p = 0.004$) for IT → PF. This dual significance implies that Lagos benefits from a coordinated and effective use of both tax reform strategies and digital systems to drive performance in its State Internal Revenue Service.

In Ogun, Oyo, and Osun States, the results also show strong and statistically significant contributions from both tax policy and IT. Ogun recorded coefficients of 0.132 ($p = 0.015$) for TAXPOL and 0.144 ($p = 0.008$) for IT; Oyo had 0.125 ($p = 0.027$) and 0.138 ($p = 0.018$) respectively; while Osun followed closely with 0.120 ($p = 0.040$) for TAXPOL and 0.134 ($p = 0.032$) for IT. These figures reinforce the idea that both policy formulation and technological deployment are key performance drivers in these mid-sized states.

In contrast, Ondo and Ekiti States showed a different trend. Although tax policy implementation remained significant, 0.128 ($p = 0.038$) for Ondo and 0.130 ($p = 0.042$) for Ekiti, the effect of IT was not significant, with coefficients of 0.085 ($p = 0.284$) and 0.071 ($p = 0.455$), respectively. This suggests that while structured tax policies continue to support performance improvements, IT interventions have yet to translate into measurable impacts in these smaller states.

Table 9. Bootstrapping: Path Coefficients Analysis of Significance (Aggregated Results)

Constructs	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
TAXPOL -> PF	0.107	0.119	0.048	2.217	0.027
IT -> PF	0.130	-0.135	0.048	2.691	0.007
IT x TAXPOL -> PF	0.066	0.076	0.058	1.145	0.252

Source: Author’s Computation (2024)

Restatement of Hypotheses and Discussions of Findings

H₀₁: Tax policy implementation has no significant effect on performance (PF).

The analysis in Table 9 reveals a positive and statistically significant relationship between tax policy implementation (TAXPOLICY) and performance (PF), evidenced by a path coefficient of 0.107, a T-statistic of 2.217, and a p-value of 0.027. These results indicate that a one-unit

improvement in tax policy implementation corresponds to an estimated 11% increase in performance. The T-statistics exceed the critical value of 1.96, confirming the strength and reliability of the relationship. The p-value, being below the 0.05 threshold, also confirms its statistical significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative, affirming that tax policy implementation significantly enhances the performance of the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) in Southwest Nigeria. This underscores the need for coherent and strategic tax policies that provide clear operational frameworks, reduce compliance uncertainties, and strengthen the overall financial management system within public revenue institutions.

These findings strongly align with the third research objective and further validate the hypothesis that tax policy implementation is a critical driver of organizational performance. Strategic tax policies (characterized by clarity, fairness, equity, consistency, and adaptability) facilitate compliance, reduce tax evasion, and promote efficient tax administration. Moreover, supporting mechanisms such as robust IT infrastructure, transparent policy communication, periodic reviews of tax legislation, and the equitable enforcement of tax laws enhance the effectiveness of tax policy implementation. These features not only support operational performance but also enable better planning, resource allocation, and accountability within revenue services. The findings are consistent with findings from Subagiyo et al. (2020), Trinh and Tan (2020), He et al. (2023), Putra (2024) in developed countries confirmed that tax policies could enhance organizational performance. Contrarily, Siggih et al. (2024), Rezeki and Harahap (2024), and Putri and Priyono (2025) found that tax policies have not significantly contributed to tax compliance, reduction or elimination of tax evasion and fraud. Be that as it may, the results are consistent with prior research in Nigeria (Obafemi et al., 2021; Panle & Okpara, 2021; Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022; Okoh & Ofor, 2024), which highlight that organizations with well-developed tax policy frameworks tend to achieve stronger financial and service delivery outcomes. However, the extent of performance improvement largely depends on how well these policies are aligned with institutional goals and operational realities.

Institutional Theory offers a valuable theoretical lens to explain the relationship between tax policy implementation and performance. This theory suggests that organizational performance is influenced by adherence to institutional norms, rules, and structures. In this context, the implementation of sound tax policies reflects conformity to regulatory and institutional expectations, thereby legitimizing the actions of SIRS and fostering improved efficiency, credibility, and performance. As institutions embed practices that align with broader environmental demands (such as fairness, transparency, and adaptability), their performance outcomes are likely to improve accordingly.

H₀₂: Information technology has no significant effect on the performance of the State Internal Revenue Services in Southwest, Nigeria.

The second hypothesis (H₀₂), which posits that Information Technology (IT) has no significant effect on the performance of State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in South West Nigeria, is rejected based on the empirical evidence from the bootstrapping results. The path coefficient for

the relationship between IT and performance (PF) is 0.130, and the corresponding T-statistic of 2.691 exceeds the critical value of 1.96, indicating that the relationship is statistically reliable. Additionally, the p-value of 0.007 falls well below the 0.05 threshold, confirming a positive impact of IT on the performance of revenue agencies. These results demonstrate that the adoption and strategic utilization of IT contribute significantly to enhancing the performance of tax authorities. This implies that investment in IT infrastructure, system quality, and human resource digital capacity has a beneficial impact on the operational efficiency, effectiveness, and service delivery of the organization. It suggests that when IT is properly implemented and integrated into tax administration, it can increase the performance of SIRS.

This finding underscores the essential role that modern technology plays in transforming public sector institutions such as SIRS. Investments in robust IT infrastructure, integrated information systems, automated processes, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) tools, and Human Resource Management Systems (HRMS) and digital reporting platforms facilitate seamless data management, enhance taxpayer engagement, reduce compliance errors, and increase transparency in tax administration. These findings are consistent with prior empirical studies in Ghana, Indonesia, Zimbabwe, and others (such as Hamza et al., 2020; Ayeni, 2021; Lucena, 2024; Duve & Schutte, 2025), and studies by Awai and Oboh (2020), Michael and Adegbie (2020) which affirm that IT adoption enhances the performance of public institutions through increased automation, accountability, and resource optimization. This finding does not align with findings by Adegboye et al. (2022) that IT adoption has no significant effect on organizational performance.

The positive relationship between IT and the performance of SIRS in Southwest Nigeria is further supported by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). According to TAM, user acceptance and utilization of technology are determined by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In the context of tax administration, when IT systems are perceived to be user-friendly and beneficial to operational efficiency, employees are more likely to adopt and integrate them into their workflows. This integration leads to higher performance through improved productivity, reduced manual workloads, and better compliance management. Thus, the significant impact of IT observed in this study is both practically relevant and theoretically grounded, reinforcing the strategic importance of digital transformation in public financial institutions.

H₀₃: Information technology does not significantly moderate the impact of tax policy implementation and the performance of the State Internal Revenue Services in Southwest, Nigeria.

The interaction effect between Information Technology (IT) and Tax Policy Implementation (TAXPOL) on the performance (PF) of the State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) in Southwest Nigeria was examined to determine whether IT significantly moderates this relationship. The analysis produced a path coefficient of 0.066 with a p-value of 0.252. Given that this p-value exceeds the conventional 0.05 threshold for statistical significance, the interaction effect is not statistically significant. In other words, while both tax policy implementation and IT adoption independently show positive and significant effects on organizational performance, their combined or interactive influence does not result in a significantly greater improvement in performance. This

suggests that the implementation of IT systems and the formulation of tax policies may not be operating in a strategically synchronized manner to yield amplified performance outcomes.

The insignificant moderating effect suggests that while SIRS invests separately in IT infrastructure and tax policies, these are not yet integrated to boost performance. This gap may arise from misaligned policies and IT capabilities, insufficient staff training, or poor collaboration between policymakers and IT teams. IT appears to be used mainly as an administrative tool rather than a strategic enabler of tax policy. To unlock full benefits, tax policies and IT systems must align strategically, with IT designed to support policy goals and policies crafted considering technological capacities. Institutional Theory highlights that harmonizing formal rules with operational systems enhances performance, emphasizing the need for integration.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study concluded that both tax policy implementation and information technology adoption have a positive and statistically significant impact on the performance of SIRS. Well-structured and consistently applied tax policies enhance compliance, reduce ambiguities, and strengthen financial governance, ultimately improving institutional performance. Similarly, the adoption and effective use of information technology contribute significantly to organizational efficiency, taxpayer service delivery, data management, and decision-making processes. However, the study concluded that the interaction effect between tax policy implementation and information technology on performance was found to be statistically insignificant. This suggests that despite the independent benefits of both variables, their synergy has not been fully harnessed to achieve amplified results. This could be attributed to a lack of strategic alignment between tax policy frameworks and the design or implementation of IT infrastructure. Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are proposed.

- i. Tax policies should be regularly reviewed to ensure clarity, fairness, consistency, and equity, fostering voluntary compliance and public trust. Enhancing stakeholder engagement and timely communication of policy changes will improve alignment and reduce ambiguity.
- ii. States must invest in modern IT systems, such as digital tax filing and data analytics, alongside training staff for effective use. An integrated strategy aligning IT infrastructure with tax policy objectives is essential, focusing on tax collection, audit management, and compliance tracking.
- iii. Finally, given the findings and conclusions, robust mechanisms for continuous assessment of tax policies and IT implementation should be established, with regular stakeholder feedback and collaboration between policymakers and IT managers to maximize performance outcomes.

By implementing these recommendations, SIRS in Southwest Nigeria can move from isolated improvements in tax policy and technology to an integrated, performance-driven tax administration system that ensures efficiency, transparency, and sustainability.

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